

1 Numerical investigation on the moisture, temperature, and pressure-dependent gas
2 desorption and transport in shale matrix subjected to microwave irradiation

3 Jia Liu^a, Xiao Liang^a, Yi Xue^{a*}, Shi-Tong Li^b, Yong Fu^{c*}, Xin Liang^a, Shanjie Su^d

4 a. State Key Laboratory of Eco-hydraulics in Northwest Arid Region, Xi’an
5 University of Technology, Xi’an 710048, China

6 b. Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, National University of
7 Singapore, Singapore 117576, Singapore

8 c. Department of Ocean Science and Engineering, Southern University of Science and
9 Technology, Shenzhen, 518055, China

10 d. School of Civil Engineering, Xuzhou University of Technology, Xuzhou, 221018,
11 Jiangsu Province, China

12 **Abstract** Microwave-thermal recovery technology, serving as an auxiliary technology
13 in conjunction with hydraulic fracturing for shale gas extraction, can enhance the
14 sustainable production of shale gas through secondary reservoir reconstruction. Given
15 the intricate coupling effects between gas and moisture within the shale matrix under
16 microwave irradiation, this study establishes a methane adsorption model incorporating
17 moisture, temperature, and pore pressure. Subsequently, a coupled multi-physics model
18 is proposed, incorporating complex gas adsorption, two-phase flow, phase-change of
19 water, and heat transfer from microwave irradiation and phases. The impacts of two-
20 phase flow within the shale matrix pores on the storage and transport characteristics of
21 moisture and gas are analyzed through numerical simulations. The influences of electric
22 field intensity and loss factor of shale matrix are investigated. The results show a
23 negative correlation between moisture and methane adsorption within the shale matrix.
24 Under high-pressure conditions, the influence of moisture on methane adsorption
25 capacity is more pronounced at lower temperatures than at higher temperatures. For the

*Corresponding author: Yi Xue (xueyi@xaut.edu.cn), Yong Fu, (fuy3@sustech.edu.cn)

26 same temperature change, an increase in pore pressure enhances the controlling effect
27 of moisture on methane adsorption capacity. This study provides essential theoretical
28 guidance for the on-site implementation of microwave-thermal recovery in shale gas
29 applications.

30 Keywords: Moisture; Microwave irradiation; Absorption-desorption; Shale gas

31 1. Introduction

32 The swift progress of industry and the economy has precipitated an escalating
33 global exigency for petroleum and gas resources, including coal, oil, and natural gas.
34 The burgeoning demand places an increasingly formidable strain on the secure
35 provision of energy resources. The depletion of coal and petroleum reserves, coupled
36 with the pressing demand for clean, low-carbon energy sources, has propelled a
37 continuous escalation in the global demand for natural gas. This has spurred the
38 exploration and extraction of unconventional natural gas resources[1, 2]. Shale gas,
39 recognized as a pivotal unconventional natural gas resource, boasts abundant reserves
40 and promising prospects for expansive development. In recent decades, the extraction
41 and utilization of shale gas have garnered significant attention from scholars globally.
42 The exploration and development of shale gas are deemed crucial for optimizing energy
43 consumption structures and contributing significantly to environmental conservation[3,
44 4].

45 Shale gas is a kind of unconventional natural gas that emerges from the thermal
46 maturation of organic matter within shale gas reservoirs, evolving through a self-
47 generation and self-storage mechanism. The predominant constituent of this

48 unconventional natural gas is methane (CH₄)[5]. The endowment manifestations of
49 shale gas within the reservoir primarily consist of natural fractures and free gas within
50 pores, coupled with adsorbed gas residing within the shale matrix or affixed to the
51 surfaces of clay particles[6]. Shale gas is characterized by an extended production
52 lifespan, wide geographical distribution, and significant resource potential. It is
53 considered to be one of the most commercially promising unconventional energy
54 sources of the present century[7]. However, shale matrices commonly exhibit
55 characteristics of low porosity and permeability[8]. This hinders the effective migration
56 of shale gas within the matrix, making it challenging to extract shale gas through
57 conventional methods. Furthermore, the shale matrix often contains a discernible
58 quantity of moisture. The presence of moisture induces a water-blocking effect,
59 resulting in a reduction of matrix permeability. This significantly impacts the
60 adsorption, desorption, and migration of shale gas, thereby influencing the extraction
61 of shale gas[9]. Therefore, it is imperative to enhance the matrix porosity and
62 permeability by modifying the characteristics of the shale gas matrix for the extraction
63 of shale gas.

64 Hydraulic fracturing refers to the injection of fracturing fluid into the subsurface
65 through wellbores at elevated pressures, thereby expanding the fracture network within
66 the reservoir. This process improves the matrix's fracture network system, thereby
67 modifying the permeability characteristics of shale gas in the matrix [10]. However,
68 hydraulic fracturing techniques exhibit certain limitations. For instance, shale gas
69 leakage and low backflow rates of fracturing fluid during the extraction process may

70 pose a risk of contaminating the groundwater environment. The substantial retention of
71 fracturing fluid in the matrix can, to a certain extent, exacerbate the water-blocking
72 effect within the shale matrix. Furthermore, The reservoir commonly hosts 20-85% of
73 shale gas in an adsorbed state within the shale matrix[11, 12]. The desorption volume
74 of shale gas will directly impact the production of shale gas wells. The exclusive
75 reliance on hydraulic fracturing is insufficient for effectively extracting shale gas from
76 the matrix, as a substantial volume of shale gas persists in an adsorbed state within the
77 shale matrix. Therefore, there is a demand for a green, efficient, and pollution-free shale
78 gas enhancement technique for the secondary transformation of reservoirs, aiming to
79 elevate the recovery efficiency of shale gas.

80 Presently, microwave-thermal recovery technology has attracted widespread
81 attention due to its rapid temperature elevation, selective heating characteristics, and
82 ease of control. Hence, the concurrent application of hydraulic fracturing and
83 microwave thermal recovery technologies serves to foster the sustainable extraction of
84 shale gas (Fig. 1). By subjecting the shale matrix to rapid heating through microwave
85 irradiation, the desorption of shale gas is facilitated. Moreover, the moisture content
86 within the matrix is influenced by microwave irradiation. As polar molecules, water
87 molecules experience intense friction under microwave irradiation, generating thermal
88 energy that facilitates the warming of the shale matrix. The elevation in temperature
89 induces the evaporation of moisture within the matrix, mitigating the water-blocking
90 effect, enhancing matrix permeability, and amplifying the rates of shale gas desorption
91 and diffusion. Therefore, to investigate the feasibility of sustainable shale gas extraction

92 through microwave irradiation, it is crucial to study various factors such as moisture
 93 within the matrix, particularly focusing on their impact on the adsorption and desorption
 94 of shale gas. Moreover, microwave irradiation also induces damage and alteration to
 95 the shale matrix, subsequently modifying the microstructure of the shale matrix[13].
 96 Nevertheless, this constitutes a complex process that has not been addressed in the
 97 present study, and its investigation will be pursued in subsequent research.

98
 99 Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of microwave-thermal recovery of shale gas

100 In recent decades, numerous scholars have extensively investigated the application
 101 of microwave-thermal recovery technology for shale gas extraction. The findings
 102 indicate that microwave irradiation enhances the pore structure and permeability within
 103 the shale, reducing the number of adsorption pores[13, 14]. Moreover, microwave
 104 irradiation can also weaken the adsorption affinity between shale gas and shale matrix,
 105 altering the adsorption-desorption characteristics of shale gas[15]. In numerical
 106 simulations, Liu et al.[16] stated that microwave irradiation significantly enhances the
 107 desorption and transport of shale gas, thereby improving the shale gas recovery
 108 efficiency. In the aforementioned study, primary consideration was given to the
 109 microwave-thermal effect on the adsorption-desorption characteristics of shale gas.

110 Temperature and pore pressure effects on the adsorption-desorption behavior of shale
111 gas within reservoirs are evident[17, 18]. Additionally, the presence of moisture in the
112 matrix introduces a discernible influence on the adsorption-desorption kinetics of shale
113 gas. In addition, the presence of moisture within the matrix can also impart a certain
114 influence on the adsorption-desorption dynamics of shale gas. Yuan et al.[19]
115 experimentally observed that moisture tends to diminish the gas storage capacity of the
116 shale matrix. This phenomenon arises from the competitive adsorption between
117 moisture and shale gas in the shale matrix, leading to the occupation of adsorption sites
118 for shale gas within the shale matrix. This is also a consequence of the shale's
119 hydrophilic nature[20]. The moisture content in the matrix also exhibits significant
120 dielectric properties, enhancing the shale's microwave absorption capability, and
121 thereby influencing the response level of the shale matrix to microwaves[21]. Presently,
122 there is limited research addressing the coupled influence of moisture, temperature, and
123 pore pressure on the adsorption-desorption characteristics of shale gas under
124 microwave irradiation.

125 Therefore, to systematically assess the coupled impact of multiple factors on the
126 adsorption-desorption characteristics of shale gas during microwave thermal recovery
127 processes, a more comprehensive investigation is warranted. Initially, a moisture,
128 temperature, and pore pressure-independent shale gas adsorption model was established.
129 Drawing from the adsorption model and accounting for the thermal desorption of gases
130 and thermal evaporation of moisture induced by microwave irradiation, an analysis of
131 the impact of two-phase flow within the matrix block on the storage and transport

132 characteristics of moisture and gas was conducted. Subsequently, a fully coupled
133 numerical model was developed. The model also encompasses the interplay among
134 electromagnetics, heat transfer, and multiphase flow. Thirdly, the fully coupled
135 numerical model was solved utilizing the finite element method. The model was
136 employed to investigate the responses of temperature, moisture, and pore pressure and
137 their ramifications on the shale gas adsorption-desorption phenomena within the shale
138 matrix during the process of microwave-thermal recovery. In addition, this study
139 investigates the influence of electric field intensity and loss factor of shale matrix on
140 microwave thermal recovery. In the remaining structural segments of this paper,
141 Section 2 elucidates the governing equations for the multi-physics fields. Section 3
142 introduces the cross-coupling relationships among multi-physics and model
143 implementation. In Section 4, the numerical investigation is conducted into the
144 influence of shale matrix and microwave parameters on the adsorption-desorption
145 characteristics of shale gas. Section 5 delineates the limitations inherent in this study.
146 The conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

147 2. Mathematical modeling

148 In the subsequent sections, a series of governing equations are derived, based on
149 the following assumptions: a) the shale is saturated with both gas and moisture; b) the
150 flow velocities of gas and liquid phases within the shale matrix conform to Darcy's law;
151 c) the gas phase constitutes an ideal gas mixture of dry methane and water vapour; d)
152 the theoretical consideration of mixtures involving different phases (gas and liquid) is

153 regarded as two distinct overlapping continua; e) the local thermal equilibrium within
 154 shale matrix is adopted.

155 2.1. Methane transport

156 The gaseous constituents within the shale matrix encompass shale gas and water
 157 vapour, with the mass continuity equation for shale gas (methane) expressed as
 158 follows[22-24]:

$$159 \quad \frac{\partial m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_a \mathbf{u}_g) = Q_g \quad (1)$$

160 where m is the methane gas content within the shale matrix, ρ_a is the density of methane
 161 gas, \mathbf{u}_g is the seepage velocity of the gas, and Q_g is the source term of gas.

162 The mass conservation equation for methane gas should account for two distinct
 163 forms of gas, namely free gas and adsorbed gas, and can be expressed as[25-28]:

$$164 \quad m = \varphi(1 - S_w)\rho_a + \rho_{ga} V_L \rho_s \frac{K(T)p_g}{1 + K(T)p_g} e^{(-\lambda\varphi S_w)} \quad (2)$$

165 where φ is the porosity of the shale matrix, S_w is the water saturation, ρ_{ga} is the density
 166 of methane gas under standard conditions, V_L is the Langmuir adsorption volume, p_g is
 167 the pore pressure in shale matrix, λ is the reduction coefficient of adsorption capacity
 168 in shale due to moisture, ρ_s is the density of shale matrix, $K(T)$ is the temperature-
 169 dependent adsorption equilibrium constant.

$$170 \quad K(T) = K_0 T^{-2} e^{-\frac{E_{ads}}{RT}} \quad (3)$$

171 where K_0 is the pre-exponential constant, T is the temperature, E_{ads} is the characteristic
 172 adsorption energy, and R is the universal gas constant.

173 Considering the context of two-phase flow, the percolation velocity of gas adheres

174 to Darcy's law:

$$175 \quad \mathbf{u}_g = -\frac{k_r^g k}{\mu_a} \nabla p_g \quad (4)$$

176 where μ_a is the gas viscosity of methane gas, k is the intrinsic permeability of the shale
 177 matrix, and k_r^g is the relative permeability of the gas phase. Given the presence of two
 178 phases, the permeability of each phase is also contingent on saturation. At this juncture,
 179 it is imperative to establish distinct definitions for the relative permeabilities of liquid
 180 (k_r^l) and gas (k_r^g) phases. The relative permeabilities are typically empirical and
 181 experimental, with their forms largely dependent on the characteristics of porous
 182 materials and the properties of the liquid phase. The functions employed in this model
 183 are conventionally considered to be consistently positive. Therefore, the representation
 184 of relative permeabilities is formulated as follows[29]:

$$185 \quad k_r^g = \begin{cases} 1-1.1 \times S_w, & S_w < 1/1.1 \\ \text{eps}, & S_w > 1/1.1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$186 \quad k_r^l = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{S_w - S_{li}}{1 - S_{li}}\right)^3, & S_w > S_{li} \\ \text{eps}, & S_w \leq S_{li} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

187 where S_{li} is the residual water saturation, and eps is the machine epsilon.

188 Substituting Eqs.(2)-(5) into Eq.(1) yields the governing equation of methane gas
 189 flow as follows[28]:

$$190 \quad \begin{aligned} & [\varphi\beta_a(1-S_w) + \rho_{ga}V_L \frac{K(T)e^{(-\lambda\varphi S_w)}}{(1+K(T)p_g)^2}] \frac{\partial p_g}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k_r^g k}{\mu_a} \nabla p_g\right) \\ & + [\rho_{ga}V_L p_g \frac{K(T)e^{(-\lambda\varphi S_w)}}{(1+K(T)p_g)^2} \left(-\frac{1}{2T} + \frac{E_{ads}}{RT^2}\right) - \varphi(1-S_w)\alpha_{Ta}] \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ & - [\rho_{ga}V_L p_g \frac{K(T)\lambda\varphi e^{(-\lambda\varphi S_w)}}{1+K(T)p_g} + \varphi] \frac{\partial S_w}{\partial t} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

191 where β_a is the compressibility factor of methane gas, and α_{T_a} is the thermal expansion
 192 coefficient of methane gas.

193 2.2. Moisture transport

194 The total moisture content in the shale matrix comprises both water vapour and
 195 liquid water:

$$196 \quad w(\phi_w) = \phi[\rho_l S_w + \rho_v \omega_v (1 - S_w)] \quad (8)$$

197 where $w(\phi_w)$ is the total moisture content, and its value for shale is obtained from Fig.

198 2. ϕ_w is the relative humidity, ρ_l is the density of the water, and ρ_v is the density of water
 199 vapour. ω_v is the vapour mass fraction, it is represented as:

$$200 \quad \omega_v = \frac{M_v \phi_w C_{sat}}{\rho_v} \quad (9)$$

201 where M_v is the molar mass of water vapour, C_{sat} is the saturation concentration of water
 202 vapour, and is expressed by the ideal gas assumption as follows:

$$203 \quad C_{sat} = \frac{p_{sat}(T)}{RT} \quad (10)$$

204 where p_{sat} is the saturation vapour pressure, is expressed as[30]:

$$205 \quad p_{sat}(T) = 610.7[\text{Pa}] \times 10^{7.5 \times \frac{T-273.15[\text{K}]}{T-35.85[\text{K}]}} \quad (11)$$

206

207

Fig. 2 Moisture absorption isotherm of shale (modified from Tang et al.[31])

208 The binary diffusion of water vapour and methane (\mathbf{g}_w) in the gaseous phase is
 209 represented as:

$$210 \quad \mathbf{g}_w = -p_g D_{eff} \nabla \omega_v \quad (12)$$

211 In unsaturated media, the common correlation for the effective diffusion
 212 coefficient (D_{eff}) is expressed by the Millington-Quirk model, as represented by[32]:

$$213 \quad D_{eff} = \frac{(1-S_w)\phi D}{\tau} \quad (13)$$

214 where D is the diffusion coefficient, $D=2.6 \times 10^{-5} [\text{m}^2/\text{s}]$, τ is the tortuosity factor, and its
 215 expression is as follows:

$$216 \quad \tau = [(1-S_w)\phi]^{-\frac{7}{3}} \phi^2 \quad (14)$$

217 Due to the overall pressure gradient inducing convection of liquid water, the flow
 218 velocity is determined by Darcy's law:

$$219 \quad \mathbf{u}_l = -\frac{k_r^l k}{\mu_l} \nabla p_g \quad (15)$$

220 where \mathbf{u}_l is the seepage velocity of moisture, and μ_l is the dynamic viscosity of moisture.

221 The capillary diffusion of liquid water in the shale matrix is expressed as[33]:

$$222 \quad \mathbf{g}_{lc} = -D_w \frac{\partial w(\phi_w)}{\partial \phi_w} \nabla \phi_w \quad (16)$$

223 where D_w is the moisture diffusion coefficient, is expressed as[32]:

$$224 \quad D_w = 1 \times 10^{-8} \times e^{\frac{-2.8+2w(\phi_w)}{\phi \rho_s}} \quad (17)$$

225 Therefore, the final governing equation of moisture transport in a porous shale
 226 matrix is obtained:

$$227 \quad \frac{\partial w(\phi_w)}{\partial t} + \rho_v \mathbf{u}_g \cdot \nabla \omega_v + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_w + \mathbf{u}_l \cdot \nabla \rho_l + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_{lc} = G \quad (18)$$

228 where G is the mass source term for moisture, the first term on the left-hand side of the
 229 equation signifies the rate of change of moisture content within the shale matrix, the
 230 second term represents convective transport of water vapour, the third term denotes
 231 binary diffusion of water vapour and methane gas, the fourth term signifies convective
 232 transport of liquid water, the fifth term represents the capillary diffusion of liquid water
 233 in shale matrix.

234 2.3. Microwave heating and heat transfer

235 Taking into account heat conduction, heat convective of gas and liquid, latent heat
 236 of moisture evaporation, and thermal effect induced by microwave irradiation, the final
 237 energy conservation equation in a moisture-laden porous shale matrix can be expressed
 238 as follows[34-36]:

$$239 \quad (\rho C_p)_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_g C_{p,g} \mathbf{u}_g \cdot \nabla T + \rho_l C_{p,l} \mathbf{u}_l \cdot \nabla T + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_{evap} \quad (19)$$

240 where $(\rho C_p)_{eff}$ is the effective volumetric heat capacity, ρ_g is the density of the gas. $C_{p,g}$
 241 is the specific heat capacity of gas, $C_{p,l}$ is the specific heat capacity of liquid water, Q_1
 242 is the heat source term resulting from the enthalpy diffusion flux generated by steam
 243 diffusion in the gas and the capillary flux generated by the presence of liquid water in
 244 the pores, Q_2 is the heat source from microwave heating, Q_{evap} is the enthalpy of
 245 vaporization, and $\mathbf{q} = -\kappa_{eff} \nabla T$ is the heat conduction team.

246 The effective volumetric heat capacity and thermal conductivity are expressed as:

$$247 \quad (\rho C_p)_{eff} = \theta_s \rho_s C_{p,s} + \phi[(1 - S_w) \rho_g C_{p,g} + S_w \rho_l C_{p,l}] \quad (20)$$

$$248 \quad \kappa_{eff} = \theta_s \kappa_s + \phi[(1 - S_w) \kappa_g + S_w \kappa_l] \quad (21)$$

249 where the subscripts s , l , and g represent the solid, liquid, and gas phases, respectively.

250 $\theta_s = (1 - \phi)$ is the volume fraction of the solid phase, and κ is the thermal

251 conductivity coefficient.

252 The thermal source term Q_I is expressed as follows:

$$253 \quad Q_I = -[(C_{p,v} - C_{p,g})\mathbf{g}_w + C_{p,l}\mathbf{g}_{lc}] \cdot \nabla T \quad (22)$$

254 where $C_{p,v}$ is the constant-pressure heat capacity of water vapor.

255 The latent heat of vaporisation is inserted as a source term into the heat transfer

256 equation:

$$257 \quad Q_{evap} = L_v G_{evap} \quad (23)$$

258 where L_v (J/mol) is the latent heat of evaporation, and G_{evap} is the source term for the

259 latent heat of vaporization, it is expressed as:

$$260 \quad G_{evap} = \frac{\partial[\phi\rho_g\omega_v(1-S_w)]}{\partial t} + \rho_g\mathbf{u}_g \cdot \nabla\omega_v + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_w \quad (24)$$

261 During the process of microwave-thermal recovery, microwave irradiation

262 interacts with molecules within the matrix block. The electromagnetic field induces

263 intra-molecular friction and collisions among polar molecules within the matrix,

264 consequently generating thermal energy. The heat converted by microwaves transfers

265 to the surrounding shale matrix through thermal conduction and convection

266 mechanisms. The transmission of electromagnetic waves is usually described by

267 Maxwell's equations. However, this study focuses solely on evaluating the impact of

268 electric field intensity on microwave heating power for small-scale shale matrix block.

269 In other words, the electromagnetic field radiated over the shale matrix block can be

270 considered uniform. Therefore, the microwave heating source, representing the

271 conversion of microwave energy into thermal energy, is expressed by the following
272 formula[37]:

$$273 \quad Q_2 = 2\pi f \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon'' |\mathbf{E}|^2 \quad (25)$$

274 where f is the frequency of electromagnetic waves, ε_0 is the absolute permittivity, ε'' is
275 the material's loss factor, E is the electric field intensity.

276 The dielectric properties of shale matrix are contingent upon its moisture content
277 under microwave irradiation[16, 38]:

$$278 \quad \varepsilon'' = \sum_{i=s,w,g} a_i \varepsilon_i'' \quad (26)$$

279 where $a_s=1-\varphi$, $a_w=S_w\varphi$, and $a_g=(1-S_w)\varphi$.

280 3. Numerical implementation and model validation

281 3.1. Cross-coupling relationships of model

282 This study presents a fully coupled model governed by Eqs.(7), (18), and (19)
283 and corresponding constitutive relations. Fig. 3 illustrates the cross-coupling
284 relationships among different physical fields in microwave-thermal recovery. Under
285 microwave irradiation, electromagnetic energy is transformed into thermal energy,
286 leading to an increase in temperature of shale matrix through thermal conduction and
287 convection. The elevation in temperature induces the evaporation of moisture,
288 eliminating the water-blocking effect. This impacts the storage and transport of
289 moisture and gas. Additionally, the increase in temperature induces a reduction in the
290 gas adsorption capacity, leading to thermal desorption of the gas, thereby amplifying
291 the desorption rate. Moreover, the transport of moisture and gas further alters the matrix
292 block's dielectric properties, subsequently influencing the efficiency of microwave

293 heating. The coupled process described above is governed by three highly nonlinear
 294 partial differential equations. These equations are challenging to solve analytically.
 295 Therefore, the complete set of coupled equations is solved using COMSOL
 296 Multiphysics.

297

298 Fig. 3 Cross-coupling relationship during the microwave-thermal recovery of shale gas.

299 3.2. Model description

300 To investigate the moisture, temperature, and pressure-dependent gas desorption
 301 and transport in shale matrix subjected to microwave irradiation, a geometric model
 302 with 100 mm × 100 mm was constructed. Assuming an initial pore pressure of 30 MPa,
 303 and subsequent placement of the model within a uniform electromagnetic field, this
 304 configuration results in the shale matrix block being subjected to heating under a stable
 305 microwave heat source. During the heating process, adiabatic conditions are applied at
 306 the model boundaries. Additionally, At the right boundary of the model, both methane
 307 and water vapor transport are subjected to flow boundary conditions. The imposition of
 308 these boundary conditions is intended to simulate the flow of methane from the matrix
 309 into the fractures. Zero flux conditions are applied to the other three boundaries. The
 310 numerical simulation parameters are listed in Table 1.

311 Table 1 Numerical simulation parameters

Parameter	ϕ	$C_{p,s}$	v	K_0	R	η
Value	0.04	1260	0.33	0.1	8.314	0.1
unit	-	[J/(kg·K)]	-	[MPa ⁻¹]	[J/(mol·K)]	-
Parameter	T_0	κ_s	k	ϕ_w	ρ_s	E
Value	50	0.4	5.0×10^{-7}	0.7	2400	30
unit	[degC]	[W/(m·K)]	[mD]		[kg/m ³]	[V/m]
Parameter	E_{ads}	D	S_{li}	ρ_{ga}	λ	f
Value	-9209	2.6×10^{-5}	0.1	0.717	15	2.45
unit	[J/mol]	[m ² /s]	-	[kg/m ³]	-	[GHz]
Parameter	$C_{p,s}$	$C_{p,l}$	$C_{p,v}$	$C_{p,g}$	κ_g	κ_l
Value	1260	4180	1900	1020	0.03	0.69
unit	[J/(kg·K)]	[J/(kg·K)]	[J/(kg·K)]	[J/(kg·K)]	[W/m/K]	[W/m/K]
Parameter	ε_s''	ε_0	ε_g''	ε_w''	V_L	μ_a
Value	0.2	8.85×10^{-17}	0	$0.05 T + 20$	0.00417	1.84×10^{-5}
unit	-	[F/m]	-	-	[m ³ /kg]	[Pa·s]

312 3.3. Model validation

313 To validate the model, fitting was conducted on existing experimental data[39-41].

314 Given the current simultaneous consideration of the coupled effects of humidity,

315 temperature, and pore pressure, there exists a pronounced scarcity of experimental

316 research on the impact of methane adsorption capacity within shale. This results in

317 challenges in identifying suitable experimental data for model validation; consequently,

318 an approach employing a segregated validation method was adopted. Fig. 4 illustrates

319 the fitting results under varying temperatures and pressures, while Fig. 5 depicts the

320 fitting outcomes under different relative humidities and pressures. From the figures, it

321 is evident that, under this validation approach, the model aligns closely with the

322 experimental data in terms of the variation trends in methane adsorption content. The

323 fitting process yielded favorable results, with negligible errors observed. This indicates

324 the model's applicability in describing the adsorption characteristics of shale under

325 varying humidity, temperature, and pore pressure conditions.

326

327

Fig. 4 Experimental data fitting surfaces for methane adsorption content at different temperatures

328

329

Fig. 5 Experimental data fitting surfaces for methane adsorption content at different relative humidity

330 4. Result analysis and discussion

331 4.1. Effect of initial relative humidity

332 Fig. 6 illustrates the impact of initial relative humidity on methane adsorption,
333 where the relative humidity dictates the moisture content within the matrix.
334 Observations from Fig. 6 (a) demonstrate that a lower initial relative humidity correlates
335 with a higher methane adsorption capacity, indicating a negative correlation between
336 methane adsorption and relative humidity. For instance, at initial relative humidities of
337 $RH_0 = 0.5$ and $RH_0 = 0.8$, the maximum methane adsorption amounts are 0.0433 m^3 and
338 0.0355 m^3 , respectively. This primarily arises from the competitive adsorption between
339 moisture and methane within the shale matrix block. Both moisture and methane
340 molecules can adsorb onto active sites on the shale surface. The moisture occupies
341 adsorption sites on the pore surface of shale matrix block, consequently leading to a

342 reduction in the adsorption capacity of methane. Furthermore, there exists a direct
 343 correlation between a lower initial relative humidity and an expedited reduction in
 344 methane adsorption with increasing temperature. This phenomenon is not only
 345 associated with the promotion of methane desorption due to an elevation in temperature
 346 but is also linked to the correlation between lower relative humidity and the decreased
 347 water saturation within the matrix. With decreasing relative humidity, the impact on the
 348 shale matrix permeability diminishes. This results in an increased permeation velocity
 349 of methane, thereby accelerating the desorption rate. From Fig. 6(b), a more intuitive
 350 observation reveals that with decreasing temperature and moisture, there is an
 351 augmentation in the adsorption capacity of methane within the shale matrix. Under the
 352 conditions of $RH_0 = 0.4$ and $T = 313.15$ K, the adsorption capacity of methane in the
 353 matrix reaches its maximum at 0.0460 m³. Altering the relative humidity and
 354 temperature serves to diminish the matrix's adsorption capacity for methane gas.

356 Fig. 6 Effect of initial relative humidity on methane adsorption

357 4.2. Effect of initial pore pressure

358 Fig. 7 illustrates the influence of initial pore pressure during the microwave-
 359 thermal recovery process on the adsorption capacity of methane in the shale matrix.
 360 Observations from Fig. 7(a) indicate that, under identical initial relative humidity

361 conditions, higher pore pressure corresponds to increased adsorption capacity of
 362 methane. For instance, at initial pressures of $p_0 = 20$ MPa and $p_0 = 40$ MPa, the initial
 363 adsorption capacities of methane are 0.05414 m^3 and 0.06031 m^3 , respectively.
 364 Simultaneously, with an elevation in temperature, there is a rapid decline in pore
 365 pressure within the matrix. Under an equivalent degree of temperature variation, higher
 366 pore pressure induces significant pressure differentials both internally and externally
 367 within shale matrix blocks. The increase in pressure differential leads to an acceleration
 368 in gas flow rate, subsequently inducing a more rapid variation in methane adsorption
 369 capacity. From the observations in Fig. 7(b), it is noted that, as pore pressure decreases
 370 and temperature increases, there is a gradual reduction in methane adsorption within
 371 the shale matrix. At a reference pressure of $p_0 = 40$ MPa and temperature $T = 313.15 \text{ K}$,
 372 the maximum methane adsorption is attained. Consequently, under conditions of
 373 elevated temperature and reduced pressure, there exists a facilitation of methane
 374 desorption.

Fig. 7 Effect of initial pore pressure on methane adsorption

4.3. Effect of multi-parameters synergic evolution on methane absorption

A ternary plot is drawn to analyze the effect of multi-parameters synergic evolution on methane absorption. First, the normalization procedure is applied to the

380 coordinate axes. The normalized temperature, $T_r = 0$, corresponds to a temperature of
381 313.15 K, and the normalized temperature, $T_r = 1$, corresponds to a temperature of
382 413.15 K. The normalized relative humidity, $RH_r = 0$, corresponds to a relative
383 humidity of 0, and the normalized relative humidity, $RH_r = 1$, corresponds to a relative
384 humidity of 0.8. The normalized pore pressure, $p_r = 0$, corresponds to a pore pressure
385 of 3 MPa, and the normalized pore pressure, $p_r = 1$, corresponds to a pore pressure of
386 53 MPa. Subsequently, numerical simulations were employed to compute the gas
387 adsorption quantity within the matrix block at a specific time. The results were
388 graphically depicted following a series of summarizations and compilations.

389 Fig. 8 illustrates the impact of multi-parameter variations (temperature, moisture,
390 and pore pressure) on the adsorption capacity of methane. It can be observed from Fig.
391 8 that, with constant temperature, the adsorption capacity exhibits an increasing trend
392 as pore pressure rises and relative humidity decreases. With constant relative humidity,
393 the adsorption capacity demonstrates an increasing trend as pore pressure rises and
394 temperature decreases. At a constant pore pressure, under low-pressure conditions, the
395 adsorption capacity exhibits an initial increase followed by a subsequent decrease with
396 rising temperature and decreasing relative humidity. For instance, under the condition
397 of normalized pore pressure at $p_r = 0.25$, the gas adsorption capacities are 0.0568 m^3 ,
398 0.0572 m^3 , and 0.0561 m^3 at $(T_r = 0.625, RH_r = 0.125)$, $(T_r = 0.25, RH_r = 0.5)$, and $(T_r$
399 $= 0.125, RH_r = 0.625)$, respectively. At present, it is observable that at lower
400 temperatures, the variation in adsorption capacity is more profoundly influenced by
401 relative humidity. Conversely, at higher temperatures, the alteration in adsorption

402 capacity is more prominently impacted by temperature. Under high-pressure conditions,
 403 while maintaining constant pore pressure, there is an observed trend of increased gas
 404 adsorption capacity with rising temperature and decreasing relative humidity. For
 405 instance, under a normalized pressure of $p_r = 0.5$, the gas adsorption capacities at $(T_r =$
 406 $0, RH_r = 0.5)$ and $(T_r = 0.25, RH_r = 0.25)$ conditions are 0.0699 m^3 and 0.0720 m^3 ,
 407 respectively. Based on the aforementioned results, it is evident that under high-pressure
 408 conditions, the influence of moisture molecules on methane adsorption capacity is more
 409 pronounced at lower temperatures than at higher temperatures. Furthermore, with the
 410 increase in pore pressure, the control exerted by moisture on shale adsorption capacity
 411 will be enhanced.

412
 413 Fig. 8 Effect of parameter variations on methane adsorption

414 4.4. Effect of electric field intensity

415 The rate of microwave heating is influenced by the electric field strength, as
 416 depicted in Fig. 9, which illustrates the impact of electric field strength on methane
 417 production under identical relative humidity conditions. As evident from Fig. 9(a), an

418 increase in electric field strength is observed to correspond to a higher initial desorption
419 rate. When the electric field intensity exceeds 40 V/m, the desorption rate curve
420 demonstrates an initial decline followed by an increase. This phenomenon arises from
421 the continuous decrease in pore pressure within the shale matrix during the methane
422 desorption process. As the pressure differential between the interior and exterior of the
423 shale matrix block diminishes, the desorption rate of gas gradually decreases. However,
424 with the rapid increase in temperature, not only does it enhance methane desorption,
425 but it also reduces the relative humidity. The decrease in relative humidity diminishes
426 the moisture content within the matrix pores, consequently augmenting the gas
427 permeation rate. This occurrence leads to an observed increase in desorption rate over
428 a certain period. When the electric field strength remains below 30 V/m, the gradual
429 pace of temperature elevation is insufficient to incite the aforementioned phenomena.
430 Observations from Fig. 9(b) illustrate that an increase in electric field intensity
431 correlates with amplified cumulative gas production. With the escalation of electric
432 field intensity, the proportion of adsorbed methane gas production within the total
433 methane yield gradually increases. This implies that the enhancement of the electric
434 field intensity may result in the increased release of methane from the adsorbed state,
435 thereby influencing the compositional aspects of the overall yield. For instance, at an
436 electric field intensity of 10 V/m, the adsorbed methane gas production constitutes 20%
437 of the total methane yield. At an electric field intensity of 60 V/m, the adsorbed methane
438 gas production represents 28% of the total methane yield. Such variations are of
439 paramount significance for comprehending the influence of the electric field intensity

440 on methane release and shale matrix behavior.
 441

442
 443

(a) Desorption rate of methane

444

(b) Proportion of methane production

445

Fig. 9 Effect of electric field intensity on methane production

446

4.5. Effect of loss factor

447

The loss factor of shale matrix determines their capacity to convert

448

electromagnetic heat into thermal energy, making the investigation of the impact of loss

449

factors on methane production particularly crucial. As depicted in Fig. 10(a), a bimodal

450

phenomenon is observed in the desorption rate curve when ϵ'' exceeds 0.4. This

451

phenomenon arises due to the amplified loss factor, enabling a greater conversion of

452

electromagnetic energy into thermal energy, consequently leading to a more rapid

453 temperature escalation within the matrix block. The curve exhibits minimal disparity at
 454 the first peak, while the second peak progressively advances with an increase in the loss
 455 factor. At ε'' values less than 0.3, the desorption rate curve manifests a progressively
 456 decreasing trend over time. This phenomenon emanates from the gradual elevation of
 457 matrix temperature, concomitant with the decrease in pore pressure, leading to a
 458 deceleration of methane seepage. Additionally, it is compounded by the reduction in
 459 relative humidity. Observing Fig. 10(b), it is evident that the augmentation of the loss
 460 factor contributes to an increase in cumulative methane production. For instance, at ε''
 461 = 0.1 and $\varepsilon'' = 0.6$, the cumulative methane production volumes are recorded as 0.156
 462 m³ and 0.172 m³, respectively. Within this context, the methane yield from the free gas
 463 phase remains relatively constant, while the methane production from the adsorbed gas
 464 phase gradually increases. Hence, altering the matrix block's loss factor can enhance
 465 methane extraction, facilitate methane desorption, and elevate cumulative gas
 466 production.
 467

468

(a) Desorption rate of methane

(b) Methane yield

Fig. 10 Effect of loss factor on methane production

470
 471
 472 As depicted in Fig. 10, it is evident that various loss factors during the microwave-
 473 thermal recovery process significantly impacts methane production. The underlying
 474 connection of this relationship may be associated with the influence of the loss factor
 475 on the conversion of electromagnetic energy into thermal energy within the matrix
 476 block. Additionally, it could be linked to variations in moisture induced by temperature
 477 changes. Therefore, the loss factor was systematically configured at values of 0.1, 0.2,
 478 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 to investigate the effects of microwave heating. As depicted in Fig.
 479 11(a), the maximum temperatures within the matrix block are recorded at 354 K and
 480 530 K for $\varepsilon'' = 0.1$ and $\varepsilon'' = 0.6$, respectively. Consequently, with an escalation in the
 481 loss factor, the shale matrix exhibits enhanced microwave absorption capabilities,
 482 resulting in accelerated matrix heating and subsequently elevated matrix temperatures.
 483 This implies that a higher loss factor will more effectively facilitate the conversion of
 484 electromagnetic energy into thermal energy. For instance, at $t = 60$ days, the relative
 485 humidity was recorded at 0.31 and 0.03 for $\varepsilon'' = 0.2$ and $\varepsilon'' = 0.5$, respectively. Therefore,
 486 with an increased loss factor, the matrix block heats up more rapidly, resulting in a more

487 pronounced variation in relative humidity. The fluctuations in temperature and moisture
 488 impact the adsorption and desorption processes of methane, leading to an increased
 489 release of methane and consequently elevating the cumulative methane production.

490
 491 Fig. 11 Effect of loss factors on temperature and relative humidity (a)Temperature; (b)Relative humidity

492 5. Limitations

493 In the context of this study, although the proposed fully coupled model
 494 incorporates features of microwave heating, gas transport, heat transfer, and moisture
 495 transport, certain shortcomings and limitations persist. For instance, The shale reservoir
 496 exhibits a multi-level pore structure comprising inorganic interparticle pores,
 497 intraparticle pores, organic matter pores, and microfractures[42, 43]. The forms of shale
 498 gas include free gas and adsorbed gas. Adsorbed gas exists in an adsorbed state on the
 499 pore surfaces, while free gas exists in a liberated state within the pores and fractures.
 500 During the microwave-assisted thermal recovery process, shale gas desorbs from the
 501 surfaces of smaller pores, progressively migrating towards larger pores and fractures,
 502 subsequently extracted through production wells. However, due to the adoption of a
 503 small-scale dimension in this model, it solely considers the shale matrix as a single-
 504 porous media. The investigation of multi-level pore structures will be contemplated

505 when the model undergoes an upgrade to a larger scale. Furthermore, the model
506 neglects the influence of matrix deformation. The pressure within the matrix gradually
507 decreases with the production of shale gas, leading to an increase in effective stress,
508 which may result in a decline in porosity and permeability[44]. Meanwhile, gas
509 desorption induces shale matrix contraction, causing micro-fractures to widen and
510 consequently enhancing permeability. Moreover, microwave irradiation may induce
511 micro-cracking within shale matrix, thereby altering the permeability of the matrix[37,
512 45]. The aforementioned processes can influence gas desorption and transport in shale
513 matrix. Therefore, there is a need for a more precise model to thoroughly elucidate the
514 multi-field coupling response mechanisms during microwave-thermal recovery of shale
515 gas. The limitations of this study serve as focal points for future research endeavours.

516 6. Conclusion

517 In this study, a comprehensive coupled model is established to investigate the
518 moisture, temperature, and pressure-dependent gas desorption and transport in shale
519 matrix subjected to microwave irradiation. Numerical simulations were conducted for
520 various scenarios based on the presented model, leading to the following conclusions:

- 521 1) The adsorption capacity of methane on shale exhibits a negative correlation
522 with relative humidity. A lower initial relative humidity corresponds to a more
523 rapid decline in the adsorption capacity of methane within the shale matrix as
524 temperature increases. At the normalized pressure, $p_r = 0.25$, the variation in
525 methane adsorption is regulated by relative humidity. As the normalized
526 temperature increased from 0.125 to 0.25, the adsorption capacity of the gas

527 increased by 2%. Conversely, as the normalized temperature increased from
528 0.25 to 0.5. The alteration in methane adsorption is subject to temperature
529 influence, leading to a reduction of 0.6%. Therefore, at lower temperatures,
530 the impact of relative humidity on the adsorption capacity of methane is more
531 pronounced compared to higher temperatures.

532 2) The collective impact of temperature, humidity, and pore pressure variations
533 on the adsorption capacity of methane is evident. Moreover, the alterations in
534 pore pressure will influence the regulatory role of temperature and humidity
535 on the adsorption capacity of methane. With the escalation of pore pressure,
536 the controlling impact of temperature on methane adsorption capacity
537 diminishes, while the controlling impact of humidity intensifies.

538 3) In the process of microwave-assisted thermal recovery, the desorption rate
539 curve exhibits minimal disparity at the first peak. The emergence of the second
540 peak is attributed to the intensified heating power, leading to a rapid increase
541 in temperature within the shale matrix blocks. The elevation in temperature
542 induces moisture evaporation, reducing the water saturation within the matrix
543 blocks and consequently enhancing the relative permeability of gas. This
544 phenomenon facilitates gas flow, thereby augmenting the desorption rate. The
545 progression of the loss factor ε'' from 0.1 to 0.6, resulted in a 10%
546 augmentation in the cumulative production of methane gas. Consequently, the
547 elevation of heating power facilitates the release and extraction of shale gas,
548 rendering the process more amenable.

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